

COPE-KNOEVENAGEL REACTION DYNAMICS. PART I. NATURE OF THE SECOND SOLVENT AND ITS ROLE

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The yield of condensation products in a Cope-Knoevenagel reaction is correlated with the boiling point, the miscibility with water and the electron-releasing capacity of the second solvent used in such reactions. A low boiling, immiscible and low electron-releasing solvent ensures a higher yield. A synthesis of a thioether is described.

Knoevenagel showed that the condensation of reactive methylene compounds with carbonyl compounds could be effected in the presence of weak bases or their salts (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1905, 76, 11, 179, 726, 1071). This was not of general applicability until Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2327) found that the maximum yield was obtained only when the reaction was carried out in presence of acetic acid and the water formed was continuously removed by slow distillation. The acetic acid is supposed to act as the ionising solvent and to catalyse enolisation. Alexander ('Principles of Ionic Organic Reactions', John Wiley & Sons, Inc., N.Y., 1950, p. 183) mentions acetamide in acetic acid as the best catalyst. However, Cope (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 3452) later introduced a second inert and immiscible solvent for the removal of water formed *in situ* and found ammonium acetate as the best agent (cf. Cragoe *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 381). This modification by Cope of the main Knoevenagel procedure has been named the Cope-Knoevenagel reaction.

As the second solvent Cope *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have recommended benzene. Since then several other solvents have been employed for the same purpose. These include toluene (Birch and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 488) and chloroform (Wideqvist, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1949, 3, 303). Cragoe *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) used cyclohexane, benzene, toluene and xylene in a condensation reaction between benzophenone and ethyl cyanoacetate. They observed that the reaction rate, as indicated by the formation of water, increased and the yield of alkylidene ester decreased with an increase in the boiling point of the solvent. The low yield was attributed by these workers to the dehydration of the ammonium acetate to acetamide, which was not a catalyst for the condensation reaction in question. The high boiling point of the solvent is obviously responsible for rapid dehydration of ammonium acetate, and hence, it partially explains the low yield obtained with high boiling liquids.

However, the function of the second solvent in these types of reaction does not seem to have been fully realised. It is the purpose of this paper to obtain quantitative data on the condensation reaction between ethyl cyanoacetate and ethyl levulinate according to Cope-Knoevenagel using a number of solvents and under more or less identical experimental conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solvents used were purified according to the directions prescribed by Fieser ("Experiments in Organic Chemistry", D. C. Heath and Co., New York, 1941, p. 357). The levulinic ester was prepared by esterifying crude levulinic acid with double distilled alcohol and concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84), the ester was worked up in the usual manner, re-esterified and distilled. The fraction of the ester of b.p. 206° was used in the investigation. The other reagents used were ethyl cyanoacetate (B.D.H.) fraction of b.p. 206-208°, ammonium acetate (E. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and glacial acetic acid (B.C.P.W.), b.p. 118°.

The thioether used as a second solvent in one investigation was prepared by a modification of the procedure described by McAllan *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 73, 3627); when the solvent was changed from water to alcohol the yield was noticed to drop from the almost theoretical value (as obtained by McAllan *et al.*) to 65% of theory. But the yield

again reached a theoretical value if some powdered potassium iodide was added. Most probably the potassium iodide acts by an ionic antagonism principle. The thioether prepared by this method had b.p. 92-93° and n_D^{20} 1.4345.

A special apparatus (Fig. 1) had to be devised for studying reactions with solvents, both lighter and heavier than water. This apparatus is a modification of the one described earlier by the author (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 129). The present apparatus acts by a siphon principle.

FIG. 1

In carrying out a reaction in presence of a solvent lighter than water, e.g., benzene, the flask is attached to A. The azeotropic mixture passes up, condenses in the condenser attached to C, falls along I, a thin funnel supported on a number of teeth in C and separates into two layers. The lower aqueous layer is frequently taken out by the stop-cock G and the upper layer of the immiscible solvent returns in the reaction flask along the siphon S.

For a solvent heavier than water, e.g., chloroform, mixed vapours from the reaction flask at A pass up into the condenser at C. The condensates fall along I and separate into an upper layer of water which is kept confined in the flask H and the lower layer of the heavier solvent returns along S into the reaction vessel. The water is taken out after the reaction is complete.

This apparatus may be used for the extraction of liquids with lighter or by heavier solvents. The case of the lighter solvents has been previously described (*loc. cit.*). With heavier solvents, however, an aqueous solution, the volume not exceeding that of H, can be extracted. At the outset of any operation, the flask with the solvent is attached to A. Another flask with the same solvent is placed at B. The stop-cock E remains closed and the aqueous solution is now poured in the bulb H. A certain amount of the solvent is also poured into it such that the zone of separation is above the siphon height S. The reflux of the solvent in the flask at A begins and after a few minutes the stop-cock E is regulated in such a manner

that the solvent level is always above S. After the necessary period of extraction the solvent is allowed to flow into the flasks.

Procedure.—Ethyl levulinate (14.4 g., 0.1M), ethyl cyanoacetate (11.2 g., 0.1M), ammonium acetate (1.9 g., 0.025 M) and glacial acetic acid (6 ml., 0.1M) together with the second solvent (75 ml.) were refluxed for 3 hours at temperatures suitable for a constant reflux. In each case the cold reaction mixture was washed with three successive 25 ml. portions of water. The residual oil after the removal of the solvent was fractionated under vacuum. The fraction of b.p. 153-54°/5 mm. was collected (cf. Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 423 gives b.p. 154-160°/5.5 mm.). The yields of the product obtained under more or less identical experimental conditions are presented in Table I (A).

Cragoe's technique (*loc. cit.*) of adding the catalyst in instalments was employed in some of the experiments; Table I (B) records the yields of the product obtained in the reactions in which the total amount (1.9 g.) of the catalyst was added in three instalments, each at an

TABLE I

Solvents	Yield. A	Yield B
1. Ether	6.7 g	..
2. Thioether	7.6	..
3. <i>n</i> -Hexane	14.8	13.3 g.
4. Petrol ether (60°-80°)	14.8	13.7
5. Chloroform	15.3	13.6
6. Carbon tetrachloride	11.4	13.0
7. <i>cyclo</i> Hexane	12.1	15.4
8. Dioxane (75 ml.) + benzene (75 ml.)	0	..
9. Acetic anhydride	0.8	..
10. Benzene	17.8;17.5;17.9	14.5
11. Toluene	16.1;15.5;15.8	13.5
12. Xylene	11.5;11.9,11.3	10.5
13. Benzene (37 ml.) + toluene (37 ml.)	11.3	10.9
14. Benzene (60 ml.) + toluene (15 ml.)	12.6	..
15. Benzene (60 ml.) + xylene (15 ml.)	12.0	..
16. Benzene (50 ml.) + <i>tert.</i> -BuOH (25 ml.)	12.2	..
17. Benzene (50 ml.) + <i>tert.</i> -BuOH (75 ml.)	2.3	..
18. Toluene (37 ml.) + xylene (37 ml.)	11.4	10.8
19. Xylene (50 ml.) + benzene (25 ml.)	12.1	12.6
20. Xylene (50 ml.) + toluene (25 ml.)	12.3	11.4
21. Benzene (75 ml.) + anisole (10 ml.)	15.4	..
22. Benzene (75 ml.) + anisole (46 ml.)	11.6	..
23. Without any solvent	3.8	..

interval of 45 minutes. The total time of reflux was the same as in the other cases viz., 3 hours. The yields in most cases are lower than that obtained with the catalyst added in one lot. The formation of high boiling by-products was encouraged by Cragoe's technique. In the case of camphor, however, yield of the condensation product always exceeded that obtained by Cragoe *et al.* themselves of larger amounts of the catalyst were used. Experimental data regarding this and a plausible explanation thereto will form a part of a future communication.

DISCUSSION

The essential prerequisite for ionic organic reactions is that the components must be soluble in the solvent used. It has been found that the yields obtained in *n*-hexane, petroleum ether (6.p. 60°-80°), carbon tetrachloride and *cyclo*hexane, used as the second solvent, were much below those obtained in the aromatic hydrocarbon solvents. In the former, the whole system remains inhomogeneous which is not the case with chloroform in which the yield is more or less higher. Similar poor yields or none at all are obtained with ether or dioxane-benzene mixture as the second solvent. Without a second solvent whatsoever the yield is low (3.8 g.). The removal of the water formed therefore seems essential. The more efficient the second solvent is in this respect, the better the yield. The failure of the oxo-ethers to remove water may be responsible for the poor yield obtained with them. However, a poor yield obtained in thioether in which water is insoluble makes the problem of removal of water a doubtful one. A glaring case which makes it still more doubtful is the negligible yield obtained with acetic anhydride as the second solvent. In fact, almost no reaction takes place, not even acetylation of the carbonyl compound used.

According to Cragoe *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) the boiling point of the second solvent is one of the factors determining the yield of the product. This is not borne out by the above experiments in which the boiling points of the solvents, viz., *n*-hexane, petroleum ether (60°-80°), carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexane, are close to that of benzene; but it is benzene which gives the highest yield.

The boiling point therefore appears not to be the sole deciding factor. The above solvents are not inert but, in fact, differ considerably as regards their electron-releasing capacity. On this basis it is found that the yield is lower, the greater the electron-releasing capacity of the second solvent, whether it is immiscible with or reactive towards water. Whenever the yield is low, either the unreacted components are left behind or high boiling reaction products are formed. The high boiling point of the second solvent probably lowers the yield indirectly through the formation of high boiling by-products, the amount of which increases with the boiling point of the second solvent. The yield data obtained with benzene, toluene and xylene confirm this (Table I). It should be mentioned that the electron-releasing capacity of these solvents are also in the order: xylene > toluene > benzene (Remick, "Electronic Interpretations of Organic Chemistry," John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1943, p. 91), the same order in which the yields increase. This point is further corroborated by the experiments with mixed solvents (Table I). They are composed of varying proportions of benzene, toluene and xylene and such electron-releasing liquids like *tert.*-BuOH or anisole. For instance, 1 : 1-benzene-toluene mixture gave a lower yield than the 4 : 1-benzene-toluene mixture. In the latter, if toluene was replaced by xylene, the yield dropped but slightly. An 1 : 1 xylene-toluene mixture gave almost the same yield (11.4 g.) as the 1 : 1 mixture of benzene and toluene (11.3 g.), 2 : 1-xylene-benzene and 2 : 1-xylene-toluene also gave almost the same yield although it should have been less in the latter.

The yield of product dropped with increasing proportions of *tert.*-BuOH added to benzene. The greater solubility of water, however, in *tert.*-BuOH should not be overlooked; but the yield is low even if water-immiscible anisole is added to benzene in place of *tert.*-BuOH.

The nature of the second solvent is concluded to greatly influence the formation of the product in the Knoevenagel-Cope reaction. Of all other properties of the second solvent, its boiling point, miscibility with water, and the electron-releasing capacity have been found to be correlated with the yield of the condensation product. For instance, a low boiling solvent ensures a higher yield by suppression of by-products. The immiscibility of the solvent with water and a low electron-releasing capacity are also favourable for higher yields.

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